

VeriFish

The sustainability indicator framework to communicate responsible aquafood production and consumption patterns

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D3.1 – Communication, stakeholder engagement plan, including branding guide and promotional material

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Aquafood sustainability, responsible aquafood production, communication, dissemination, stakeholders, target audiences, outreach, communication activities, live tool.

Disclaimer

VeriFish offers a framework of verifiable sustainability indicators for communications about sustainability based on FAIR data from EU- and global aquafoods repositories, brought together through the extraordinary collaboration of European-wide actors like NOFIMA, EUROFIR and Poseidon. Leveraging on this indicator, VeriFish designs, develops, and disseminates a number of media products to help citizens, aquafood consumers and retailers, associations and policy makers make informed consumption choices.

GLOSSARY OF TERMS

Item	Description
CNR-IRBIM	Istituto per le Risorse Biologiche e le Biotecnologie Marine del Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche
CoP	Community of Practice
CTA	Call To Action
CWA	CEN Workshop Agreement
DC	Design Committee
Dx.x	Deliverable number (the first digit indicates WP)
EAB	External Advisory Board
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable
FAO	Food and Agriculture Organisation (United Nations)
GA	General Assembly
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GDST	Global Dialogue on Seafood Traceability
GRSF	Global Record of Stocks and Fisheries
GSSI	Global Sustainable Seafood Initiative
HoReCa	Hotel, Restaurant, and Café/Catering
ICES	International Council for the Exploration of the Seas
ICT	Information and Communication Technologies
ISO	International Organization for Standardization
KB	Knowledge base
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
MAC	Market Advisory Council
MSC	Marine Stewardship Council
Mx	Month of the project (M1 = May 2024 and M24 = April 2026)
NDA	Non-Disclosure Agreement
NGO	Non-Governmental Organisation
OA	Open Access
RDF	Resource Description Framework
SDOs	Standards Development Organizations
SEO	Search Engine Optimization

Item	Description
SFP	Sustainable Fisheries Partnership
SGPO	Standard Good Practice Organisations
STECF	Scientific, Technical and Economic Committee for Fisheries
UN	United Nations
WBA	World Benchmarking Alliance
WG	Working Groups
WP	Work Package

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The VeriFish Communication and Editorial Plan aims to effectively disseminate project results and engage with stakeholders through various media channels. These live tools will ensure communication aligned with project activities and stakeholder needs.

A co-ordinated 24-month Communication, Dissemination, Outreach and Education strategy under WP3 has been designed, built around specific communication and exploitation campaigns for raising awareness of the project, measurable results, overall scientific benefits and impacts, and measures for reaching end-users and other stakeholders.

Key activities include designing a visual identity, developing a public website, executing social media, publishing newsletters and articles, creating educational and promotional media products, and organising events, such as the VeriFish conference. Regular monitoring through analytics tools, Google Analytics, will enable adjustments to optimise communication strategies.

This comprehensive plan will ensure that all stakeholders can be informed and potentially engaged throughout the project lifecycle, maximising impact of project activities and outputs. This is the first version of the Communication plan (D3.1), which will be updated as needed during the project. Results arising from this Communication, Dissemination, Outreach and Education strategy will be reported in D3.6 Communication, stakeholder engagement final report (M24).

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1. Objective

The primary objective of the VeriFish project is to stimulate increased consumption of sustainable aquafood by establishing a framework of verifiable indicators, as a basis for targeted, accessible, and engaging media products and campaigns, as well as delivering European good practice recommendations describing how to communicate efficiently about aquafood. The project will create and distribute comprehensive media products and engage in awareness campaigns, providing verifiable information about aquafood. This initiative aims to bridge the gap between actors in the various aquafood chains and consumers by offering transparent and reliable data on sustainability and other interests (e.g., healthy affordable foods). The project seeks to provide information for stakeholder groups, including citizens, retailers, policymakers, and industry professionals, about the benefits of sustainable aquafood production and consumption. By leveraging diverse communication tools and strategies, VeriFish intends to help foster informed decision-making, promote healthy eating habits, and support environmental stewardship.

2. Plan Overview

The VeriFish communication plan focuses on **target audiences** (Figure 1) of the project to ensure communication efforts are directed towards individuals and organisations that will maximise impact. For that, the project has identified a series of stakeholders at local, national and EU levels. The goal is to develop detailed profiles for each group to help understand their needs and communication preferences.

Subsequently, the plan **elaborates selected outreach campaigns** developed during the proposal phase including communication activities, messages and formats, and tools, based on audience characteristics. The plan provides a road map for optimising timings of the campaigns to ensure maximum visibility and potential engagement. For that, a schedule for campaign activities, including dates, milestones and KPIs has been established.

Finally, to coordinate and align messaging, and to ensure a cohesive approach, the plan has developed **clear, compelling, and targeted messages** that explain the project's aims and expected or actual results. These highlight benefits of sustainable aquafood consumption, the importance of verifiable information, and the role of VeriFish in promoting these. The plan ensures that messages are consistent across all communication channels and materials.

Figure . Communication Plan Overview

To complement the communication plan, an **editorial plan** has been developed with the goal of establishing a structured approach to content creation, distribution, and monitoring. This will ensure effective dissemination of project activities and results. This editorial plan is presented as part of the communication plan and outlines types of content, including news articles, interviews, social media, participation and promotion at events and other materials (e.g., leaflets). The plan schedules regular content updates and coordinates with partners to align content production with project milestones and events. In addition, it will help coordinate delivery of scientific papers and their dissemination as well as plan non-peer-reviewed publications to disseminate new knowledge and innovations. Open Access (OA) publication of datasets and publications through repositories like Zenodo will also be monitored for reporting, as described in the project data management plan (D1.2).

3. Identification of Target Audiences/Stakeholders:

3.1. Stakeholder analysis

By targeting stakeholder groups with tailored messages, campaigns, and media products, VeriFish will effectively demonstrate how to raise awareness and promote adoption of sustainable aquafood practices. The proposed approaches will ensure that each group's needs and preferences are addressed, fostering broad support and engagement with the project. Industry and producers will serve as the central point for interaction because of their role in the aquafood value chain. By engaging closely with these groups, the project aims to influence up- and downstream stakeholders effectively, promote sustainable aquafood practices, and support increased consumption of local products. The expanded stakeholder mapping outlines key groups involved, their interactions, and specific strategies for engagement.

We have categorized stakeholders (Figure 2), focusing on their interests and concerns related to VeriFish. Key topics for each group include sustainable fishing practices, nutrition, economic benefits, regulatory compliance, fish health and human consumption, industry collaboration, research participation, advocacy for supportive policies, and training opportunities. The analysis (ANNEX 1) helps understanding of specific interests and concerns of each stakeholder group, allowing for more targeted and effective communication strategies.

Figure 2. Stakeholders identified by VeriFish project

3.2. Stakeholder Relationships and Dynamics

Stakeholders within the seafood sector are interconnected in numerous ways (Figure 3), forming a complex web of interactions that significantly influence sustainability practices. Understanding these relationships is crucial for shaping the activities and strategies of the VeriFish project. The following section outlines how VeriFish perceives these interactions from a sustainability perspective and how they inform our approach and activities.

Industry and producers connect with **consumers** primarily through communication and engagement efforts, providing crucial information about the sustainability and health benefits of their products. This relationship has influenced VeriFish's strategy to develop consumer-facing media products, such as factsheets, educational posters, and recipe books, which aim to increase consumer awareness and promote informed purchasing decisions of sustainably sourced products. By targeting these efforts, VeriFish seeks to build consumer trust and drive demand for sustainable seafood.

To engage the next generation, **industry and producers** interact with **children** via parents and educators, and through support for educational programs that provide information about sustainable aquafood. VeriFish has leveraged this dynamic by creating child-friendly media products, such as interactive

flashcards, maps, and educational games, designed to foster early awareness and positive habits regarding sustainable seafood choices.

Industry and producers engage with **policymakers** through advocacy to influence regulations and standards that support sustainable practices. In turn, they comply with these policies to demonstrate their commitment to responsible practices. This dynamic has guided VeriFish's approach in developing advocacy campaigns and policy briefs, aimed at shaping regulations and fostering dialogue between the industry and policymakers. These efforts are complemented by participation in industry forums and conferences to advocate for supportive policies.

Fisheries and Aquaculture Associations and Producers: Like the broader industry, these groups advocate for supportive policies and collaborate with NGOs to advance environmental and sustainability agendas. VeriFish integrates this collaboration into its activities by organising joint workshops and training sessions that involve these associations, aiming to enhance knowledge sharing and align industry practices with sustainability standards.

Academic institutions provide essential research and data that inform policy decisions and industry practices. VeriFish actively engages with academic partners to incorporate the latest scientific evidence into its sustainability indicators and guidelines, ensuring that project outputs are grounded in robust research. This collaboration also extends to the development of publications and participation in academic conferences, where VeriFish disseminates findings and gathers feedback.

Media outlets play a critical role in disseminating information to the public and influencing consumer behaviour and policy decisions. VeriFish leverages this relationship by developing targeted media outreach strategies, including press releases, feature articles, and video content, to amplify its sustainability message and reach a broader audience.

VeriFish recognises the importance of collaboration with **NGOs, academic institutions, and SDOs** to advance research, develop standards, and promote good practices. The project actively collaborates with these stakeholders to co-create guidelines and standards that support the wider adoption of sustainable seafood practices. This approach is reflected in the project's efforts to align its indicator framework with existing standards and in its participation in SDO meetings to influence the development of new standards.

By understanding and leveraging these stakeholder dynamics, VeriFish has designed a comprehensive engagement strategy that integrates these interactions into its activities, ensuring that the project effectively promotes sustainable seafood practices across the sector. This approach not only supports the dissemination of project results but also enhances the impact and adoption of sustainable practices among all stakeholders involved.

3.2.1. Central Role of Industry/Producers

As can be seen in the stakeholder interaction map (Figure 3), **Industry/Producers** act as the central link in the stakeholder network, connecting various groups and facilitating flow of information and good practices. Their involvement is crucial for the success of project Communication and Dissemination

strategies as they influence both the supply and demand sides of the aquafood market. **Industry** (Figure 3) has a central role regarding consumers as it shapes how individuals receive information about aquafood and decide what information is going to be made available, underpinning trust generated towards different products. Through these mechanisms of *Communication* and *Engagement*, the **Industry** controls provision of verifiable and clear information and generates campaigns to deliver this. Additionally, **Industry** interacts with **Children** through *Education* and *Promotion* including packaging of aquafood products and sustainability. In the same way, **Industry** can collaborate with policymakers and *Advocates* to shape regulations and enforce *compliance* with the existing ones. *Collaboration* of the **Industry** with **Other Stakeholders** helps to advance research, develop standards, and promote good practices. *Media relations* help to highlight how sustainability can be achieved, as **Industry** can model or influence how such messages reach different audiences.

Figure 3. Stakeholder interaction map

4. Communication Strategies and Campaigns

VeriFish Communication Plan has been built around specific **communication and exploitation campaigns** that will be the backbone of the 24-month communication, dissemination, outreach and education strategy. This plan will raise awareness of the project and reach end-users and other stakeholders while providing measurable results, demonstrable via verifiable KPIs. The plan is organised around four outreach campaigns providing a mix of activities to address stakeholders’ needs and will bring benefits in terms of engagement and impact. Additionally, the campaigns will support monitoring and enable adjustment of actions to make an efficient use of resources.

4.1. Campaign 1: VeriFish project communication

This campaign focuses on creating a consistent project identity and communicating the scope and impact of VeriFish through branding, website, social media, newsletters, and press releases. The goal is to ensure the scope and expected impacts are communicated via official channels with a consistent identity, describing project activities and potential benefits for citizens, for example. The campaign lasts **24-months** (M1-M24, Figure 4) and targets **all stakeholders** with the main message:

VeriFish is innovating communications about sustainable and responsible seafood production and consumption via a free, verifiable, and dynamic framework for the seafood value chain.

Figure 4 VeriFish overview of the main dissemination, exploitation and communication activities of Campaign 1.

4.1.1. Project Branding

Establishing a VeriFish visual identity is necessary to consolidate awareness among stakeholders, whilst still tailoring specific messaging to target audiences using call-to-actions and promotional materials.

The acronym "VeriFish" should always be written with a capital “V” and “F” to maintain consistency and brand integrity.

The VeriFish logo (Figure 5) includes three fish-element pictograms presented in a circle, giving the idea of sustainability as a continuous and interlinked mechanism. It features two shades of a primary colour associated with the sea, i.e., vibrant blue and a deep navy.

Figure 5. VeriFish logo

The logo also appears in three distinct versions, each tailored for specific uses.

- Horizontal logo, which includes space for a comprehensive branding statement, or strapline.
- Compact, square logo without the strapline, ideal for smaller spaces where clarity is needed.
- VeriFish Avatar, which is a simplified representation suitable for icons and avatars.

These different versions have been used in the design of project templates, such as PowerPoint and Word (Figure 6), on- and offline, as well as for design of the website and social media presence.

The logo, specifically the VeriFish Avatar, is being utilised across various social media platforms to ensure consistent brand representation. This avatar version is featured in social media banners on LinkedIn, X, Instagram, Facebook, and YouTube. By using the avatar on these platforms, VeriFish maintains a cohesive and recognisable presence online, reinforcing brand identity, and making it easier for users to identify and engage with the brand.

KPIs

- Project branding package with logos, templates, and collaterals available: 1 kit
- Roll-up banners (layout) and posters distributed at conferences: 2 by M12, 5 by M24
- Number of printed copies & online downloads of flyers & policy briefs: 3000 by M12 and M24

At the time of writing (August 2024, M3), the project branding guide has been made available to partners while a roll-up has been published and the first flyer is being prepared.

VeriFish branding materials will be available from the public website.

Figure 6. VeriFish Word template

4.1.2. Project public website:

The VeriFish website serves as the primary online hub for showcasing the project. It is designed to provide stakeholders with comprehensive information about the project's goals, progress, outcomes, and events.

On the 28th of June 2024, the VeriFish webpage (Figure 7) (<https://verifish.info/>) was launched with the sections describing the project, ways of contacting us, web-app, news and other additional information. It also includes a section underlying *why aquafood is important* that contextualises the project (Annex 2 includes a description of the sitemap structure). The webpage, using Google Analytics, gathers information, via **cookies**, for users that enable basic functionalities of the site, and analyses how users engage the website to enhance and monitor interaction with the website. The website is controlled by **Eurofish International Organisation**.

Launch of the webpage was announced on **LinkedIn** and **X** and shared through partners’ social media channels. All information showcased in the social media channels, described in the next section, are updated on the website, helping to maintain a high search engine optimization (SEO) ranking. Additionally, partners use compelling calls-to-action (CTAs) to guide visitors to the webpage, promoting the link and information about the webpage through their SoMe channels and related activities.

The content strategy for the website follows a high-quality, relevant content pathway based on goals and results from the project, highlighting success stories, project milestones, and updates published as news, findings and advances. It will also include all public materials produced by the project for download and will support links between partners and stakeholders.

KPIs for Website:

- Sessions per month: >1k by M12, >3k by M24

Figure 7. Homepage of the VeriFish webpage

4.1.3. Social Media

Social media platforms are essential for engaging with wider audiences, promoting project activities, and disseminating information about the VeriFish project. The goal is to maintain an active presence on various social media channels to build a robust network of followers, facilitate interactions, and drive engagement through multimedia campaigns.

Project social media accounts (Figure 8) were launched on the 6th of May 2024 (see ANNEX 3: Social Media Links). Following a platform-specific strategy to maintain active engagement on multiple platforms, the project uses **LinkedIn** and **X** as its main social media platforms. However, it is also present on **Facebook**,

Instagram, and **YouTube**. **LinkedIn** is used to share articles, project reports, and insights into project developments as well as general information and information about sustainable aquafood practices with the goal of connecting with industry professionals. **X** is used to complement **LinkedIn** activities and for real-time updates using hashtags to increase visibility and join trending conversations. Both **Instagram** and **Facebook** are used for visual content, such as photos from project activities and infographics. Together with these, **Instagram Stories** are used to promote content, organise polls, and give “behind-the-scenes” at project meetings. Finally, **YouTube** will be used to publish video content developed by the project.

KPIs for SoMe

- Followers across all platforms: >500 by M12, >1000 by M24

Figure 8. VeriFish project’s social media channels. From left to right and up to down: Facebook, Instagram, X and LinkedIn (YouTube is not showcased as the project did not produce content to this date)

4.1.4. Newsletters

To keep stakeholders informed about project activities, VeriFish will publish newsletters in a reader-friendly format. These newsletters will provide updates on project milestones, success stories, upcoming events, and other relevant information. The goal is to ensure regular and engaging communication with all stakeholders.

KPIs for Newsletters:

- Number of Newsletter published by M24: 12

4.1.5. Press releases

To engage relevant media and publishers within the aquafood community, VeriFish will publish press releases that highlight newsworthy results or events. These will increase visibility and, hopefully, generate interest in the project from a broader audience, ensuring key achievements and updates are widely communicated. This approach will help to create a media presence and keep some of the public (e.g., older adults) informed about significant project milestones and developments.

The first press release was published on 22nd May with information about the kick-off meeting. It has been published in several outlets such as [Eurofish Magazine](#), [Industrias Pesqueras](#) and [AquaFeed](#) (Figure 9)

KPIs for Press Releases:

- Number of press releases sent: 2 press releases sent by M12, 5 by M24.

Figure 9. VeriFish press release publication n AquaFeed.com

4.1.6. Third Party Events

To effectively disseminate results and the activities of VeriFish, the project will participate in third-party events that target our main stakeholders. These events might include industry conferences, trade shows, academic symposiums, and relevant community gatherings. By being present, and presenting at these events, VeriFish aims to share its findings, engage with stakeholders, and promote sustainable aquafood.

This level of engagement will ensure that VeriFish maintains a prominent presence with the industry and fosters valuable connections with stakeholders, facilitating broader adoption and impact of sustainability initiatives and, consequently, consumption of such products.

The project attended the kick-off meeting of its “sister” project Mr Goodfish (22.05.2024) and gave a presentation to the Market Advisory Council (MAC). The project is also planning to be present at:

Table 1. Third party main events the project plans to attend

Event	Event type	Date	Link
Aqua 2024	Fair	August 26-30, 2024	https://aquaeas.org/Program/Sessions
Eurofish International Conference	Conference	September 24-26 2024	https://eurofish.dk/spanish-conference-2024/
Conxemar	Fair	October 01-03, 2024	https://www.conxemar.com/en/congress-2024/
Seafood Expo global 2025	conference	May 06-08, 2025	https://www.seafoodexpo.com/global/

KPIs for Third Party Events:

- Number of events attended by project partners: 20 by M24

4.2. Campaign 2: Co-creation and consensus gathering on the VeriFish Indicator framework (incl. factsheets)

During the research and planning phase for the indicator framework, VeriFish will engage with data providers as well as aquafood and aquaculture producers to support provision, validation, and assessment of the VeriFish indicators and framework, and identify concrete pilot cases for adoption. Ultimately, VeriFish will produce a series of pilot factsheets. The campaign will be oriented to aquafood retailers, consumers and consumer associations, fisheries and aquaculture associations, and producers during all the duration of the project (M1-M24), underpinned by the message:

Increasing awareness on the health benefits and nutritional value of aquafood is a multi-faceted process that requires consistent effort and collaboration among actors in the value chain and stakeholders. The VeriFish indicator framework will allow you to access information on provenance, production, and species as nutrient content, thereby harmonising ways to communicate about aquafood food sustainability.

4.2.1. Community of Practice (CoP)

To foster an engaged community of consortium members, implementation partners, observers, and other stakeholders in the process of co-design, assessment, validation, and promotion of the indicator framework, factsheets, and media products, VeriFish will establish a Community of Practice (CoP). This will bring together individuals interested in planning and designing aquafood awareness or marketing campaigns, particularly aquafood producers and retailers committed to promoting sustainable aquafood. The CoP is expected to have a significant impact both during and after the project. The CoP will also foster support for dissemination of the VeriFish indicator framework, media products, web-app and attendance at the final conference. Regular review will inform the consortium as to how members are using the CoP, and shape the support provided accordingly.

Activities

CoP development is driven by members and their interests but facilitated by the consortium. It will be mobilised via several mechanisms, e.g., CoP meetings and workshops to discuss progress, gathering feedback, and sharing insights, social media, consultations distributed via the project website, etc., whilst always respecting GDPR.

A CoP database is currently being created (Figure 10) and will be maintained as a project resource tracking users by stakeholder type, as well as being at disposal of the consortium for activities such as requirement specification, feedback and assessing the effectiveness of guidelines.

To improve the communication between members of the CoP and the communication of the project toward them, a LinkedIn communication group will be created no later than M12 to increase interaction and facilitate an online gathering platform. The group will foster communication and facilitate dissemination of findings and discussions among participants. The project envisions a (maximum) target of having 800 members actively participating in the LinkedIn Group dedicated to the CoP, fostering professional networking and collaboration.

Figure 10. Preview of the VeriFish CoP database under construction

STAKEHOLDER	Stakeholder type	Further details	Social media handle - relevant hashtags	Related outreach campaigns (see section 2.2.2) - to be completed later	Contact person
Kagerer & Co. GmbH Consorzio Pescatori di Goro	1.seafood retailers	Seafood products retailer The cooperative, leader in the shellfish sector and markets at national and European level.	LinkedIn: https://www.linkedin.com/company/kagerer-co-gmbh/ Instagram: https://www.instagram.com/co.pe.go?igsh=OTQ1amtmcTZxOG5l Facebook: https://www.facebook.com/copego.goro Youtube: https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCMFPnCap_iFelDw-MUy9M_Q		Andrea Schimmelpennig Sandro Suncini
DELPIERRE	1.seafood retailers	Delpierre is specialised in smoked and salted seafood products.	Facebook: https://www.facebook.com/delpierrefrance Instagram: https://www.facebook.com/delpierrefrance		Elodie Tessereau
Food Trade International Ltd	1.seafood retailers	It is a B2B structure where F.T.I. offer suppliers a place to market their products and for customers to source quality approved fresh and frozen food products.			Sean Cooke
FRINSA	1.seafood retailers	Grupo Frinsa, one of the largest European manufacturers of canned fish and shellfish, especially tuna fish.	Instagram: https://www.instagram.com/conservasfrinsa/ Facebook: https://www.facebook.com/FrinsaLaConserva/ X: https://x.com/ConservasFrinsa Youtube: https://www.youtube.com/FrinsaLaConserva LinkedIn: https://www.linkedin.com/company/frinsa-del-nordeste/		Jose Aller
FROSTA	1.seafood retailers	One of Europe's leading manufacturers of innovative, nutritious frozen food of the highest quality.	Facebook: https://www.facebook.com/frosta.it/ Youtube: https://www.youtube.com/channel/UC3hgEPwWBHKyy4ZUBVUCIEg Instagram: https://www.instagram.com/frosta_italia/		Helene Eulenstein
Froxa	1.seafood retailers	Pescado y marisco congelado - https://froxa.com/empresa/	Instagram: https://www.instagram.com/froxa.es?hl=es LinkedIn: https://www.linkedin.com/company/froxa-s-a-7original/Subdomains		Maite Magadan
Seafoodia	1.seafood retailers	Seafood distribution	Facebook: https://www.facebook.com/seafoodia/ Instagram: https://www.instagram.com/seafoodiaofficial/ X: https://x.com/Seafoodia LinkedIn: https://www.linkedin.com/company/seafoodiacompany/?viewAsMember=true Youtube: https://www.youtube.com/c/Seafoodia		Our Story - Seafoodia
CRIOC (Centre de Recherche et d'Information des Organisations de Consommateurs)	2. Consumers and consumer associ...	CRIOC carries out scientific studies and analyzes at the request of the various committees and working groups, the consumer organizations and the Federal Public Service Work, Economy and Consumers. Topics covered include consumer perception and behavior patterns when purchasing or using goods or services, as well as purchasing power, advertising and sustainable consumption.			
ECU (European Consumers Union)	2. Consumers and consumer associ...	ECU aims at uniting European consumer organizations for collaborating on all matters related to consumerism and on the pan-European citizenship. https://europeanconsumersunion.eu/?lang=en	https://europeanconsumersunion.eu/		Manuela Colella ; Sergio Veroli

KPIs for Community of Practice:

- Overall VeriFish CoP members database (registered to the website and web app): 3000 by M24.
- Number of VeriFish CoP members on LinkedIn group: 800.
- Number of actors listed and identified in the CoP database: 100.
- Number of consumers networks and associations engaged: 20 in 10 countries by M24

4.2.2. Requirements gathering workshops

To effectively gather requirements and ensure the VeriFish indicator framework meets the needs of stakeholders, we will conduct a series of online workshops. These workshops will engage aquafood producers, as well as representatives from retailer and consumer associations. Through these interactive sessions, participants will provide valuable input and feedback on the framework's design and implementation, helping to tailor it to industry needs and consumer expectations.

More specifically, we will host workshops to gather requirements and inputs from partners and external stakeholders, focusing particularly on the needs and insights of aquafood retailers, HoReCa, fisheries associations, and aquaculture producers. At least three online requirements gathering, and design workshops will be organised to collaboratively assess the indicator framework and design media products. These activities will include interactive methods such as brainstorming sessions, focus groups, and surveys to capture diverse perspectives.

The workshops will be documented and reported in the final stakeholder engagement deliverable of the project (D3.6, to be published in M24, April 2026), and the outcomes will be incorporated into the framework development process, ensuring that industry-specific concerns and recommendations are prioritised. A design committee will be set up, integrating VeriFish partners, members of the External Advisory Board (EAB), and key stakeholders from external networks. This committee will collect and

evaluate the needs of stakeholders regarding the proposed media products, conduct design thinking and user experience workshops, write functional specifications, and produce mock-ups.

The gathered requirements and specifications will inform D3.2 and D3.3.

An initial requirements gathering workshop was already organised with VeriFish partners to start drafting the specifications of the web app on 11th July organized by COMMpla, bringing together Eurofish, EUROFIR, Nofima, FORTH, and Clupea partners to brainstorm on users, added value for target users, and basic functionality. A collaborative online whiteboard tool (Mural) was used to collect feedback.

The following figure (Figure 11) presents some of the initial outcomes.

Figure 11. Outcomes of the 1st internal requirement gathering workshop (Mural Whiteboards)

KPIs for Requirement gathering workshop:

- Number of participants per stakeholders (fisheries, aquaculture, retailers, consumers) in the 3 online **requirements gathering and design workshops**: 2 participants per each of the stakeholders (4) selected, 8 participants total.

4.2.3. Community Validation Workshops

Community validation workshops are critical to ensure the relevance of the VeriFish indicator framework. These workshops will target retailers, consumers, and producers in Europe and beyond, as well as the experts engaged in the EAB, focusing on real-world application and usability. These workshops will also provide valuable insights from users, and ensure the VeriFish indicator framework is robust, practical, and has the potential to be widely accepted.

To achieve this, we will organise on-site and online workshops in collaboration with entities such as Community Catch (<https://communitycatch.org/>), an initiative harnessing market demand to support sustainable development of small-scale fisheries, and other relevant networks. In-person workshops will be organised in conjunction with other community events in Europe Union. At the time of writing, VeriFish has started working with Community Catch to plan a validation session at the SeaFood Expo Global (April 2025, Barcelona, Spain) to leverage their planned community-based activities. The goal is to present the draft framework, gather feedback on its feasibility, relevance, and usability, and demonstrate application of framework in real-world scenarios, particularly retail environments and aquaculture.

During these workshops, participants will engage in pilot testing to provide insights on the framework's practical application. The workshops will serve as a platform to validate the proposed indicators and framework with stakeholders, ensuring they meet the needs of the industry and consumers.

Key activities will include:

- Presenting the draft framework to stakeholders.
- Gathering feedback through interactive sessions and discussions.
- Conducting pilot tests to showcase the framework's application.
- Collecting detailed feedback to refine and improve the framework.

KPIs for Community Validation Workshops:

- Average number of participants: 20
- Conducting up to three workshops in collaboration with Community Catch or other relevant networks.
- Ensuring a balanced representation of retailers, consumers, and producers in each workshop.

4.2.4. External Advisory Board (EAB) Statements

VeriFish has established an external advisory board (EAB) composed of 10 knowledgeable and passionate European-based experts with influential ties and direct channels to different stages of the aquafood value chain, including producers, retailers, and consumers. The EAB also includes other actors who can shape responsible production and consumption of aquafood products, such as NGOs, policymakers, and standards & good practices organisations. The consortium has invited high-level individuals to ensure a fair representation of the overall European aquafood sector and to help deliver positive impact in the sector.

The primary function of the EAB is to engage industry experts, researchers, and policymakers to provide strategic advice across all project phases. They will offer guidance on creating the CoPs, validating the indicator framework, contributing to media products, and raising visibility and awareness of project activities. The EAB will meet virtually every six months and at General Assemblies (GAs). Each member has signed an NDA to maintain confidentiality on technical and other information.

Karl Presser from Premotec (CH & PL) is chair of the EAB.

Key activities of the EAB include collecting written statements in the form of articles, interviews, and blog posts from its members. These statements will be distributed across the VeriFish network to leverage the experts' visibility and reputation, particularly those from the industry sector.

KPIs for External Advisory Board statements:

- Collecting and distributing at least 10 expert statements throughout the project duration.

The project has allocated a budget for the payment of nine person-days (@450€/day/per person) for the duration of the project to support the EAB's activities.

At the time of writing the following experts have confirmed their willingness to join the EAB:

- Anton Ellenbroek, Consultant at FAO
- David Basset, EATiP General Secretary
- Richard Stavis, engagement leader at the Global Dialogue on Seafood Traceability (GDST) initiative
- Irene Kranendonk, Impact Manager at Fish Tales // Board Member Fish Tales Foundation
- Andrea Fabris, API Associazione Piscicoltori Italiani, Director
- Anne Marie Cooper, ICES Expert Program Manager in International Oceans, Fisheries, and Aquaculture Science, Policy, and Management
- Fabio Grati, CNR IRBIM of Ancona - chair of STECF and involved in the development of indicators for the EU
- Pedro Reis Santos, Secretary General of the Market Advisory Council (MAC)

Discussions are ongoing to onboard as members from Community Catch and Sustainable Fisheries Partnership (SFP).

4.3. Campaign 3: Awareness raising towards Consumers, Citizens and Children

This campaign aims to increase awareness about the benefits of sustainable aquafood using dynamic factsheets, web applications, awareness videos, influencer partnerships, and educational programmes.

The purpose is to enhance knowledge about nutrition, health, and sustainability aspects of aquatic food through the prototype VeriFish web application and various media products. The campaign will utilise multiple channels, including social media, educational networks, community events, and allied healthcare settings, to reach a broad audience. The campaign targets primarily Consumers, Citizens and Children. Thus, it will also influence retailers, consumer associations, and fisheries and aquaculture associations and producers. It will start in M5 (September 2024) and last until the end of the project (M24).

Efforts will be made to capitalise on local, national, and international health and awareness days to amplify messages. Collaboration with healthcare professionals, and nutritionists and dietitians will be key to incorporating aquafood information into their recommendations. Additionally, the campaign will

provide consumers and aquafood producers associations with white-label awareness materials for their communication activities. The main message of the campaign reflects all these objectives:

4.3.1. VeriFish Dynamic Factsheets:

The VeriFish project will create and distribute multilingual dynamic digital factsheets available on the

Fish and seafood food chains, their health benefits and risks, and environmental impacts are complex. Thanks to VeriFish (prototype) web app and media products you can increase your understanding of these issues to make choices about consumption based on your concerns

VeriFish (prototype) web app, by exploiting the Global Record of Stocks and Fisheries (GRSF) semantic knowledge base (KB). This KB already hosts records from all major EU data providers, making it a robust platform for disseminating verifiable information on fisheries and aquaculture. The dynamic factsheets will combine and organise data around various aspects of the aquafood production chain, including legislation, compliance, environmental sustainability, socio-economic factors, and health and nutrition. These factsheets will be designed to provide users with clear, reliable, and up-to-date information, enabling them to make informed decisions about their aquafood consumption.

As a prototype action, VeriFish will demonstrate the feasibility of generating multilingual and dynamic factsheets. Initially, the factsheets will be monolingual and have a static design, with content extracted primarily from the GRSF. Over time, these factsheets will be enriched with data from additional repositories and expanded to include dynamic elements, such as the latest content and templates, which can be updated regularly. By Year 2, users will be able to select their preferred language and indicators, with templates translated into all EU languages. Content will initially be translated into the languages of the consortium (Italian, French, Dutch, Norwegian, Danish, Greek, Polish), but the system is scalable to accommodate more languages as users contribute translations via the CoP.

The factsheets will not only provide core indicators on sustainability but also ancillary information for unverified indicators, such as links to YouTube videos, recipes, and other non-indicator content. They will be accessible online as searchable, SEO-friendly web pages with filters and tags to facilitate easy navigation. This approach aims to validate the concept of multilingual dynamic factsheets and test the effectiveness of using such tools to enhance consumer awareness and informed decision-making regarding sustainable aquafood.

KPIs for the Dynamic Factsheets:

- 10 factsheets created, covering 7 fisheries and 3 aquaculture streams.

4.3.2. Prototype Web Application:

The VeriFish (prototype) app for mobile and web (Figure 12) will facilitate informed decisions about aquafood consumption by providing verifiable information on sustainability, provenance, and health benefits. The user-friendly app will serve as a resource for all stakeholders, offering detailed insights

based on indicators for aquafood and related information, along with suggestions for choices using standardised terminology for sustainability and health.

The app will feature a convenient and intuitive interface, presenting information derived from the VeriFish semantic platform. This platform builds on an extended version of the GRSF, enhanced with data from various sources, including FishBase and EuroFIR datasets. The VeriFish KB will also generate content for media products, such as videos, posters, and infographics.

By reproducing the VeriFish indicator framework in an easy-to-navigate format, the app will provide comprehensive information on the status of fish stocks, fishing activities, food composition, biological characteristics of species, and environmental conditions. Users will access information through QR codes, which link to detailed product descriptions, labels, indicators, and multimedia content, including videos, food composition data, health benefits, risks, and recipes. Initially, the QR codes will be generic for species, aligned with the FAO GRSF, FAO AGROVOC, WorldFish Fisheries and Aquaculture Ontology, FishBase/SeaLifeBase, and ISO12875 and ISO 12877.

Figure 12. Mock-up representation of the VeriFish web app user panels

The web app aims to be a rich media product that delivers scientifically validated information for outreach campaigns suitable for post-project re-use and exploitation by actors in aquafood chains. The VeriFish prototype will be accessible from any computer or mobile device, leveraging a dedicated API to facilitate access to and searching of the VeriFish KB. The prototype will demonstrate applicability of the indicator framework, aiming to provide quick, easily understood, accurate, and up-to-date indicators with links to verified information. The VeriFish KB will be constructed and maintained using semantic web technologies, meaning data from original sources will be harvested, normalized, and transformed using a common schema (ontology). Data will be described in the form of RDF triples (<subject, predicate, object>), supporting the answering of complex queries using SPARQL. The dedicated API will formulate SPARQL queries, interpret results, and deliver them in JSON format, usable by the web application and directly by end users.

- **Tuning between Blue-Cloud Data Lakes and DTO development, 2nd report**

4.3.3. Awareness Raising Videos

VeriFish will produce short pitch-style videos and interviews with project partners, experts, activists, and nutritionists. These videos will frame VeriFish assets within the wider context of sustainable fisheries, encouraging citizens and ocean science enthusiasts to make informed consumption choices that support a sustainable future. The videos will be landed on YouTube and distributed via the other VeriFish social media channels to maximise reach and engagement.

The first video will be published in October 2024 with the script ready at the beginning of September.

KPIs for Awareness Raising Videos.

- 30 video assets available by the end of the campaign.
- Track the number of video views to measure engagement and reach.

4.3.4. Influencer Videos

VeriFish will engage influencers to create videos or podcasts that highlight best practices related to nutrition, sustainability, and biodiversity. Whenever possible, these influencers will be encouraged to share stories and insights with their communities via their social media channels, helping to amplify VeriFish messages and reach a broader audience. By leveraging influencers' established networks, VeriFish aims to increase awareness and engagement around sustainable aquafood practices.

The project will focus on influencers related to marine sustainability and aquafood consumption that have already worked with NGOs or a well-know aquafood promoters (e.g. Chefs) and that have a well-established platform (minimum of followers 10k). The project will perform an influencer mapping process before M10 to be able to launch a call for influencers and invite them to produce and distribute videos on nutrition, sustainability and biodiversity aspects. The main SoMe channel for the distribution of these videos will be **Instagram** with the backup of both **Facebook** and **X**.

KPIs for Influencers videos:

- Engage 5 influencers to participate in the campaign.
- Track the number of videos or podcasts produced and the engagement metrics for each piece of content.

4.3.5. Eurofish Magazine

VeriFish will leverage the EU-wide bi-monthly journal, Eurofish Magazine, to disseminate key project insights and promote sustainable aquafood choices. Eurofish Magazine, which circulates 500 copies per edition, is a well-regarded publication within the fisheries and aquaculture sectors. As part of VeriFish's communication strategy, at least five articles will be published in the magazine by project partners. These articles will guide readers on how to make informed decisions when choosing aquafood, with a focus on different market segments and stakeholders.

At the time of writing this report, the project has published one article (Figure 13) in the Eurofish Magazine’s August issue (<https://eurofish.dk/magazine-issues/em-4-2024/>). The next article is planned for November-December (M7-M8). Other publications are planned for M11, M15 and M19, but these dates might vary depending on content and progress of the project.

A possible sixth publication about the results is foreseen for M41-M42.

KPIs for Eurofish Magazine:

- Publish a minimum of five articles in Eurofish Magazine.
- Achieve 3,500 impressions on the magazine's website related to these articles, helping to spread awareness of sustainable aquafood practices.

Figure 13. Front of the VeriFish article on the Eurofish Webpage

4.3.6. Instagram Video Challenge

VeriFish will launch an Instagram video challenge titled “How to Communicate About Sustainable Fish,” running from M12-24. This challenge will target chefs, those in the fishing industry, nutritionists, and students, inviting them to pitch creative ways to communicate the importance of consuming sustainable aquafood. Participants will share their videos on Instagram, showcasing their insights on sustainable fishing practices. Winners of the challenge will be featured at the VeriFish conference, and in an issue of Eurofish Magazine, further amplifying their message.

KPIs for Instagram Video Challenge:

- Engage at least 20 participants in the video challenge.
- Track overall engagement rates and the impact of the challenge on raising awareness about sustainable fishing.

4.3.7. Storytelling Sessions

VeriFish will host a series of storytelling sessions on its main website, centred around ocean adventures and aquafood-themed stories designed to encourage children to explore and eat aquafood. These stories, aimed at fostering early awareness about sustainable aquafood, will be crafted in five languages and leverage real-world examples. The storytelling sessions will be distributed across VeriFish social media channels, newsletters, and partner networks to reach a broad audience.

An example of a channel to use in these activities is **Fish Tales** (<https://www.fish-tales.com/>), an organisation that works with fishing communities in developing countries to raise consumer awareness about the current state of our oceans and the importance of sustainable fishing. Fish Tales might be involved in the storytelling and dissemination activities, contributing their unique stories and experiences.

KPIs for Storytelling sessions:

- Creation and publication of at least three short stories.
- Distribution of stories via social media, newsletters, and partner networks.
- Engagement metrics from the storytelling sessions to measure their impact on raising awareness about sustainable aquafood among children and European citizens.

4.3.8. Promotion and Development of VeriFish Media Products

The promotion and development of VeriFish media products will involve a comprehensive approach to ensure that stakeholders, including education channels, associations, and NGOs, are effectively engaged in promoting the (prototype) web app and related media products. These products are designed to digest complex information from the VeriFish aquafood indicators into accessible, easy-to-understand formats for user communities.

Design and Development Process:

A design committee (DC) will be established to coordinate the development of these media products, integrating VeriFish partners, members of the EAB, and stakeholders from external networks. The DC will evaluate the needs of stakeholders, conduct design thinking and user experience workshops, write functional specifications, and produce mock-ups. The EAB will provide strategic guidance throughout the process, ensuring that products are aligned with VeriFish visibility and awareness-raising goals.

Workshops and Requirements Gathering:

At least three requirements-gathering and design workshops will be organized with aquafood producers, as well as representatives from consumer associations. These workshops will focus on gathering input for the design of media products to ensure they meet the needs of stakeholders. The outcomes will be incorporated into the development process, ensuring specific concerns are prioritized. These workshops will be made in collaboration with the web-app validation workshops described in 4.2.2. While the first ones only reflect on the design and application of the web-app, these workshops will expand the information gather and focus on all the media products produced, or to be produced by the project.

The requirements and specifications will be refined and updated until Month 18 (M18).

Types of Media Products:

Media products to be developed will include infographics, flyers, posters, and common templates for deliverables and meetings. Additional materials will be created for both online and offline use, such as the VeriFish web app, social media challenges, videos, flashcards, games, and educational materials for children and consumers. These products will translate the complexity of aquafood supply chains, health benefits, and environmental impacts into formats that are easy to understand and widely accessible.

As for the time of the writing, the first flyer is being drafted for publication in September (M5).

Distribution and Engagement Strategy:

Promotion of these media products will be achieved through active engagement with education channels, associations, and NGOs that can help distribute materials via news, newsletters, and social media. The goal is to maximise the reach of these products by encouraging their adoption, further distribution, and re-use under the entities' branding. The media products will be distributed with free culture licences to promote re-use by multiplier networks, ensuring future replicability and sustainability.

Media Products and Content Multiplier Approach:

The media products will be designed following a content multiplier approach. This includes:

Factsheets (see 4.3.1): Collecting data and insights from the indicator framework for each species.

Flashcards game (free culture licence) (Figure 14): Educational tools for children to promote ocean health and sustainable aquafood choices. The goal is to educate children about the importance of ocean health through sustainable aquafood choices.

Figure 14. Mock-up representation of the VeriFish flashcard game - sample layout of back and front.

Maps and Calendars: Raising awareness about the provenance and seasonality of aquafood through indicator data on seasonality and geographical spread of aquafood. Data on the seasonality and geographical distribution of aquafood will be utilized to create a downloadable calendar that provides information on the best fish to consume during specific times of the year. Additionally, an interactive geographical map, which will also be available as a puzzle game, will illustrate the locations of various aquafood species across the globe. Both the calendar and map will be offered in a white-label format with a free culture licence, allowing stakeholders to distribute them freely.

Recipe Books: A children's recipe book will be created in collaboration with nutritionists and food experts, particularly those associated with the SEAFOODTOMORROW network. This book will feature simple, nutritious aquafood recipes that are easy for children to prepare with adult supervision, catering to children's taste preferences while offering a variety of aquafood options. The recipes will focus on preparing undervalued local aquafood products with low environmental impacts, providing consumer-friendly methods to enjoy these sustainable choices. Additionally, the book will include international recipes inspired by global cuisines, showcasing species such as herring, mackerel, mussels, trout, and carp. This recipe book will be available as a downloadable PDF from the VeriFish website and web-app, ensuring easy access for stakeholders in general, and to promote well-informed and sustainable aquafood consumption.

Educational Posters: Educational posters on fish, fisheries, and aquafood will be created and distributed for free to schools, NGOs, professional cooks, and consumer associations. These posters will focus on sustainability topics and highlight the importance of supporting local fishermen. The posters will be made available through educational networks, schools, and via the SEAFOODTOMORROW network (EuroFIR) and their associated organisations, aiming to educate the public on sustainable aquafood practices and the value of sustainable fisheries.

Guidelines: Providing user communities and stakeholders with guidelines on the use of verifiable aquafood indicators. Campaign 3 aims to provide comprehensive guidelines on the use of verifiable aquafood indicators, targeting a wide range of stakeholders including user communities, industry experts, scientists, and policymakers. These guidelines will be based on the VeriFish indicator framework

and will offer clear instructions on how to effectively communicate sustainability using these indicators. The goal is to empower both industry professionals and consumers through delivery of accurate and transparent knowledge, enabling them to make informed decisions about aquafood consumption. (see more at 4.4.2)

The guidelines will serve as a reference for communicating sustainability across different sectors, ensuring that all parties involved—retailers, consumer associations, aquafood producers, and policymakers—have a holistic understanding of sustainable practices. This initiative is designed to promote transparency, traceability, and ethical practices within the aquafood industry, thereby contributing to the long-term sustainability of marine ecosystems.

To maximise their impact, the guidelines will be made available in multiple languages and will be distributed through various channels, including consumer associations, industry events, and targeted awareness campaigns.

Web App (see 4.3.2): A prototype app for mobile and web platforms.

KPIs for the Promotion of VeriFish media products:

- Number of entities engaged: 100 entities across 20 countries by Month 24 (M24).
- Development and Adoption: The media products will be iteratively developed with feedback from stakeholders, ensuring they meet the needs of the intended audience.
- Visibility and Awareness: The EAB and Design Committee will ensure the media products align with the broader visibility and awareness-raising goals of VeriFish.
- Product Drafts: As of the writing of the Communication Plan, a flyer is being developed and discussed among partners (Image 14)

4.3.9. PPC SoMe campaigns

These media campaigns will leverage pay-per-click advertising across platforms such as Meta (Facebook), Instagram, and LinkedIn to significantly broaden the reach of VeriFish. These campaigns are designed to target specific stakeholder groups with tailored messaging, ensuring the right audiences are engaged and follow project's updates and initiatives. By focusing on high-impact ads, the campaign will drive traffic to the VeriFish website and social media channels, promoting key media products and calls to action (CTAs).

KPIs for PPC SoMe Campaigns

- Conversions per media product CTA (web app access, download of materials): 20k for M24.

4.4. Campaign 4: Policy Advocacy, Long-term Sustainability, and Expansion

The primary goal of this campaign is to advocate for inclusion of aquatic food sustainability aspects within European aquafood labelling and dietary guidelines, ensuring that sustainability is a fundamental component of these. The campaign aims to collaborate closely with the aquafood producing and processing industry to enhance communication regarding sustainable fishing and aquaculture practices,

Thanks to transparent information sources delivered by VeriFish, aquafood nutrition and sustainability aspects can be incorporated easily into messaging. Better awareness about the role that aquafood can play in a healthy and sustainable diet will support choices made by consumers. It also recognizes that European fisheries and aquaculture products are often produced in more sustainable and socially responsible ways than imported products.

promoting responsible sourcing throughout the supply chain. Additionally, this campaign is designed to sustain long-term efforts to reinforce awareness about the nutritional benefits of sustainable aquafood and collaborate with international organisations to address global nutrition challenges related to aquafood consumption. The campaign targets aquafood retailers, consumers through consumer associations, fisheries and aquaculture producers and associations, policy stakeholders and funding agencies, and SDOs and standard good practice organisations. The campaign will be carried out from M1-24, ensuring sustained focus on embedding sustainability within the aquafood sector:

4.4.1. VeriFish conference:

The VeriFish project will organize a hybrid conference in M23 to bring together industry experts, policymakers, consumer associations/organizations, and other relevant stakeholders. This conference will serve as a platform to present the VeriFish good practice recommendations and guidelines, share the project's findings, and promote dialogue on innovative solutions promoting the use of verifiable indicators in aquafood promotion. The event will include a dedicated exploitation session, possibly tied to the Eurofish conference, to further explore opportunities for adoption and implementation of these practices.

KPIs for VeriFish conference:

- Number of participants: 200.

4.4.2. Guidelines on how to use the indicators

VeriFish will produce comprehensive guidelines on the use of verifiable indicators for aquafood products, grounded in the framework developed in WP2. These guidelines aim to provide a wide array of value chain actors, including retailers, consumer associations, aquafood producers, and policymakers, with accurate and transparent resources to effectively communicate information about aquafood. By focusing on specific groups, the guidelines will help stakeholders understand which indicators to emphasize and how to visualize them, including a scoring system for normative indicators.

The guidelines will be designed to assist use of correct terminology across various languages, ensuring consistency and clarity in communication campaigns. Available in English and translated into multiple EU languages, the guidelines will be widely distributed through different associations and events, as well as VeriFish awareness campaigns. These resources will empower industry experts and consumers alike to make informed decisions, promoting transparency, traceability, and ethical practices.

In addition to supporting individual communication efforts, the guidelines will serve as a reference point for scientists and policymakers in developing systems for on-product sustainability information. Integration of these guidelines within the VeriFish web application, dynamic factsheets, and various media products—including the European Good Practice standard recommendation (CWA)—will enable the project to support a broad spectrum of stakeholders, from members of the aquafood value chain to consumers and policymakers, ultimately contributing to a more sustainable future for marine ecosystems. **KPIs for Guidelines on how to use indicators:**

- Number of downloads and printed distributed copies of the Guideline: 3000

4.4.3. Impact monitoring

VeriFish will implement a comprehensive impact monitoring strategy to maximize the effectiveness of outreach and dissemination efforts while ensuring optimal use of resources. This approach will be rooted in ongoing feedback loops and collaboration with a range of stakeholders, ensuring the project remains aligned with its high-impact goals.

Impact Monitoring Activities:

VeriFish will monitor the reach and effectiveness of initiatives using various methods, including surveys, focus groups, and social media analysis. This ongoing assessment will enable the project to refine messaging, and strategies based on real-time data and feedback. The aim is to produce eight quarterly internal reports on impact monitoring, which will detail results and guide any necessary adjustments.

Collaboration and Resource Optimization:

To avoid duplication of effort and ensure the efficient use of resources, VeriFish will actively involve partners and link with existing research projects and initiatives such as projects like PerformFish, FishEUTrust, and SmartAqua4FuturE, which provide valuable insights into consumer behaviour, aquafood sustainability, and aquaculture practices. Additionally, the project will also engage with networks such as the World Benchmarking Alliance (WBA) and aquafood Task Force to benchmark progress and expand outreach.

Impact Pathways:

The VeriFish project has been designed to achieve significant societal impact, aligning with EU policies and the UN Sustainable Development Goals. The societal impact will be realised through its various outreach campaigns, including factsheets, magazine articles, recipes, games, videos, and social media content targeting diverse consumer groups. A critical element of this strategy is the establishment of the CoP (Section 4.2.1). The CoP will serve as a platform for knowledge sharing, collaboration, and innovation, with the potential to continue generating impact well beyond the project's conclusion.

In summary, VeriFish's impact monitoring and exploitation strategy is designed to ensure that the project not only achieves its immediate goals but also leaves a lasting legacy in the field of sustainable aquafood practices. By leveraging continuous feedback, strategic partnerships, and a robust sustainability plan, VeriFish aims to make a significant and enduring impact on the aquafood industry and beyond.

KPIs for Impact monitoring:

- Number of quarterly internal reports on impact monitoring

VeriFish partners will actively participate in joint dissemination strategies and activities with other EU projects and initiatives aligned with the European Green Deal, the EU Mission "Restore our Oceans and Waters by 2030," and the Farm to Fork strategy, ensuring complementarity and avoiding overlaps.

4.4.4. Boosting visibility of the CEN Workshop Agreement (CWA)

To boost the visibility of the CEN Workshop Agreement (CWA, WP4), we will leverage services provided by the EC CSA HSBooster.eu project, which offers crucial support in standardisation and promotion efforts. As standardisation has a pivotal role in advancing the EU's political and regulatory vision, particularly in digital technologies and ICT, this collaboration will enable VeriFish to align with and promote the European approach on a global scale.

VeriFish, in partnership with Standards Norway, which is the secretariat for standards relating to fish and aquafood, will capitalise on this collaboration to facilitate creation and promotion of the CWA. The HSBooster.eu project will assist by conducting a comprehensive mapping exercise of existing standards within the technical field relevant to VeriFish. This will help evaluate the project's position within the standardisation landscape and identify opportunities for engagement with standardisation bodies and technical committees.

Additionally, the HSBooster.eu services will facilitate initial contacts and meetings with standardisation organisations and provide expert advice to help VeriFish navigate the standardisation process. This includes potentially facilitating budget for enrolling with the Standards Developing Organizations (SDOs) and Working Groups (WGs) as well as purchasing copyrighted materials, such as norms and standards.

KPIs for Boosting visibility of the CWA:

- Completion of a mapping exercise of existing standards relevant to VeriFish.
- Successful facilitation of contact and initial meetings with relevant standardisation bodies and technical committees.

4.5. Communication Strategies and Channels

The communication strategies for VeriFish are designed to disseminate project results, engage stakeholders, and promote sustainable aquafood practices through tailored messaging and multiple channels, including social media, newsletters, websites, and events. Structured into short-term, medium-term, and long-term phases, the plan outlines specific actions, timelines, and KPIs to measure success. This phased approach ensures effective communication and adoption of sustainable practices among diverse stakeholder groups, with continuous monitoring and refinement to achieve the project's objectives. Table 2 and Figure 15 illustrate the comprehensive communication plan and its implementation.

Table 2. VeriFish Communication Strategies table summarising the key objectives, actions and KPIs for each phase of the strategy.

Phase	Objective	Action	KPIs
Short-term (3-6 months)	Establish a strong project identity and online presence. Launch initial awareness campaigns. Begin stakeholder engagement.	Project Branding and Visual Identity: Develop and finalize branding materials (logo, templates, etc.).	Completion of branding package; distribution of materials at 2 industry events.
		Public Website Launch: Develop a user-friendly, SEO-driven website showcasing project assets and events.	Website live with at least 5 pages; monthly sessions target of 500 by Month 6.
		Social Media Presence: Establish engagement on Facebook, X, Instagram, Snapchat, LinkedIn, YouTube.	Achieve 500 followers across all platforms by Month 12; 1,000 conversions from PPC social media campaigns.
		Initial Awareness Campaigns: Release introductory content about VeriFish across all channels.	Engagement metrics (likes, shares, comments); website traffic target of 500 visits per month; 200 newsletter subscribers by Month 6.
Medium-term (6-12 months)	Expand outreach efforts. Increase content publication frequency. Organize stakeholder events.	Social Media Expansion: Increase posting frequency, engage followers through Q&A sessions, polls, etc.	Increase social media followers by 50%; maintain an engagement rate of 10% on posts.
		Regular Newsletters and Articles: Publish bi-monthly newsletters and articles in industry publications.	6 newsletters published; 5 articles in industry magazines; 25% newsletter open rate.
		Stakeholder Workshops and Events: Host workshops to gather input on the VeriFish indicator framework.	Conduct 4 workshops; participate in 3 major industry events; collect feedback from 100 stakeholders.
		Dynamic Factsheets and Web Application: Develop and distribute dynamic factsheets via the VeriFish web app.	10 factsheets created; web application monthly visits target of 1000 by Month 12.

Long-term (12-24 months)	Maintain momentum, continue engaging stakeholders, refine strategies based on feedback.	Sustained Website and Social Media Activity: Keep channels updated with new content and resources.	Monthly website updates; maintain a social media engagement rate of 12%.
		Continued Newsletters and Articles: Publish regular updates to keep stakeholders informed.	12 newsletters published; 10 articles in various publications by Month 24; 30% increase in newsletter subscribers
		Impact Assessment and Strategy Refinement: Evaluate and optimize communication strategies.	2 comprehensive impact assessment reports; 5 refined strategies implemented; 20% increase in stakeholder satisfaction.
		Policy Advocacy and Long-term Sustainability: Organize a hybrid conference in Month 23 to share findings.	200 participants at the conference; collaboration with 5 international organizations.
		Media Products and Educational Materials: Distribute educational posters, recipe books, and storytelling sessions.	Distribution to 100 entities across 20 countries; 3000 copies of guidelines on using verifiable aquafood indicators distributed.

Figure 15. VeriFish Communication Strategies mind map

4.6. Exploitation

The **VeriFish** exploitation plan is structured around two complementary pillars. The first involves *individual exploitation plans* where each partner utilises their networks and community connections. The second is a *joint exploitation path* designed to maximise outreach and dissemination of the project's key outputs, identifying and engaging relevant stakeholders.

Individual Exploitation Plans

Each partner will leverage established networks to support dissemination and adoption of VeriFish results. These networks include marine data practitioners, policymakers, industry associations, and research communities. Partners will integrate the VeriFish guidelines and indicator framework into existing resources and distribute these accordingly. The project outputs, including the prototype app, CoP and CWA will be shared widely to promote sustainable aquafood practices beyond the project lifespan. Open Access repositories and platforms like Zenodo will be used for publications, ensuring broad accessibility and re-use. Collaboration with organisations such as the Norwegian Seafood Council will help in distributing the indicator framework and prototype app to stakeholders.

Joint Exploitation Plans

The VeriFish app will be maintained as an online prototype for five years post-project, with considerations for publishing it as an application. This app will be linked from the VeriFish project website and partner sites and uploaded to the Horizon Results Platform of the European Commission. The indicator framework will be promoted across consumer, fisheries and aquaculture associations, enhancing data sources for initiatives like the Global Sustainable Seafood Initiative (GSSI) and the Marine Stewardship Council (MSC). The Guidelines on how to communicate sustainability using verifiable aquafood indicators, and the CWA will serve as references for scientists and policymakers. The flexible semantic technology underpinning the VeriFish KB and web app will allow integration with other resources, supporting the EC's Sustainable Food Systems Initiative. This ensures reliable transfer of sustainability information from producers to consumers, fostering growth in sustainable aquafood practices and trust.

5. Define Key Messages

In any communication strategy, defining key messages is crucial to ensure that the core objectives and values of a project are consistently and effectively conveyed to the target audiences. For VeriFish, key messages play a pivotal role in communicating the importance of sustainable aquafood practices, benefits of using verifiable indicators, and overall impact of the project on stakeholder groups. These messages are tailored to resonate with each audience, from aquafood retailers and consumers to policymakers and educators. By aligning the key messages with their interests and concerns, VeriFish aims to foster understanding, engagement, and collaboration, ultimately driving adoption of sustainable aquafood practices and supporting the project's long-term goals.

5.1. Guide to Writing Specific and Targeted Example Messages for Each Stakeholder Group

When crafting specific and targeted messages for different stakeholder groups, it is crucial to consider their unique interests, needs, and concerns. Figure 16 describes a detailed approach to developing effective communication messages that resonate with each stakeholder group.

Figure 16. VeriFish guide for effective writing of messages

5.2. Platform-Specific Guides

Use of the following steps and the structures and examples helped craft specific and targeted messages for stakeholder groups across different social media platforms. This approach ensures that the communication is effective, engaging, and resonates with each audience segment.

5.2.1. LinkedIn

Professional Tone: Use a formal and professional tone suitable for business communication.

Detailed Content: Provide comprehensive information with a focus on industry relevance and professional impact.

Visuals: Incorporate relevant images, infographics, or professional headshots to enhance engagement.

Engagement: Encourage connections to comment, share their thoughts, or get involved in discussions and activities.

Example:

"Dear [Stakeholder],

As a key player in the aquafood industry, your role in promoting sustainable practices is crucial. VeriFish is excited to introduce verifiable indicators designed to provide transparent and credible information about the sustainability of your aquafood products. By adopting these indicators, you can enhance consumer trust and showcase your commitment to responsible sourcing. We invite you to join our upcoming workshops to learn more about implementing these indicators. Together, we can set new standards for the aquafood market. Thank you for your dedication to sustainability. We look forward to collaborating with you."

5.2.2. X and Instagram Threads

Concise Messages: Keep the messages short and to the point, adhering to the character limit.

Hashtags: Use relevant hashtags to increase visibility and engagement.

Visuals: Include images, GIFs, or short videos to capture attention.

Links: Provide links to more detailed information or related content.

Example:

"Excited to introduce VeriFish indicators for sustainable seafood! Enhance consumer trust & showcase responsible sourcing. Join our workshops to learn more! #SustainableSeafood #VeriFish"

5.2.3. Facebook:

Conversational Tone: Use a friendly and approachable tone to engage a broader audience.

Engaging Content: Share stories, testimonials, or experiences related to the project.

Visuals: Use photos, videos, or live streams to make the posts more engaging.

Calls to Action: Encourage followers to like, comment, share, or participate in related activities.

Example:

"Hey everyone! We're thrilled to introduce VeriFish indicators, making it easier to choose sustainable seafood. By adopting these indicators, seafood retailers and producers can enhance consumer trust and promote responsible sourcing. Join us in our upcoming workshops to learn more about these exciting developments. Let's work together to set new standards for the seafood industry. Together, we can make a difference! 🐟 #SustainableSeafood #VeriFish"

5.2.4. Instagram

Visual Focus: Prioritise high-quality images and videos to tell your story.

Short Captions: Keep captions concise but informative.

Hashtags: Use relevant hashtags to reach a broader audience.

Stories and Reels: Use Instagram Stories and Reels for behind-the-scenes content or quick updates.

Example:

"🐟 Excited to introduce VeriFish indicators for sustainable seafood! 🐟 Enhance consumer trust & promote responsible sourcing. Join our workshops to learn more and make a difference in the seafood industry. Together, we can set new standards! 🌍 #SustainableSeafood #VeriFish"

5.3. Targeted Key topics for each stakeholder group of VeriFish:

Table 3 summarises key messages, target topics and recommended communication channels for each stakeholder group, providing a clear overview of key messages and communication strategies and ensuring effective communication of goals and activities as well as their alignment with interests and needs of each group.

For **seafood retailers**, the focus is on the sustainability benefits of sourcing and selling sustainable aquafood, enhancing consumer trust, and leveraging market differentiation. **Consumers and consumer associations** are engaged with messages highlighting the health benefits of sustainable aquafood, environmental impact, and the importance of transparency and sustainability labels. **Children, parents, and educators** are targeted with content about sustainable aquafood, including family-friendly recipes, interactive learning activities, and health education. **European citizens** are encouraged to raise public awareness, make responsible consumption choices, and engage in community initiatives that support sustainable aquafood practices. **Fisheries associations** and **producer organisations** are focused on best practices, economic benefits, and compliance with sustainability standards, while **aquaculture associations** are similarly engaged with messages about sustainable farming techniques, economic advantages, and regulatory adherence. **Policy stakeholders** and **funding agencies** are addressed with topics related to developing supportive policies, identifying funding opportunities, and promoting advocacy for sustainability. Finally, **standard good practice organisations** are encouraged to develop and

promote standards for sustainable aquafood, share best practices, and support certification programs to ensure these standards are integrated into regulatory frameworks.

Table 3. Key messages, target topics and recommended communication channels

Stakeholder Group	Key Topics	Example Message	Recommended Platform
Seafood Retailers	Sustainability benefits, consumer trust, market differentiation, staff education, compliance, marketing support	"Join us in driving the future of sustainable seafood! By adopting VeriFish's verifiable indicators, you can offer your customers transparent and credible information about the sustainability of your seafood products. Let's work together to promote responsible sourcing and elevate consumer trust in our industry."	LinkedIn
Consumers and Consumer Associations	Health benefits, transparency, environmental impact, ethical choices, advocacy for better labelling	"Did you know that sustainable seafood not only benefits the environment but also boosts your health? With VeriFish indicators, you can now make informed choices about the seafood you consume. Join us in advocating for better labelling and transparency in seafood sourcing."	Facebook and Instagram
Children (Parents/Educators)	Educational content, family-friendly products, interactive learning, health education, environmental awareness	Dive into the world of sustainable seafood with your kids! Our VeriFish educational content and family-friendly recipes make learning about sustainability fun and delicious. Get involved in our interactive activities and teach your children the importance of protecting our oceans."	Instagram, Facebook and X
European Citizens	Public awareness, responsible consumption, community engagement, health and nutrition benefits, cultural relevance	"Support sustainable seafood practices and make a positive impact on our oceans! VeriFish provides transparent and verifiable information to help you make informed choices. Join us in promoting responsible consumption and protecting marine environments."	X, Facebook and Instagram

Fisheries Associations and Producer Organizations	Best practices, economic benefits, regulatory compliance, industry collaboration, research participation, policy advocacy, staff training	"Collaboration with fisheries associations is key to promoting sustainable fishing practices. VeriFish indicators enhance transparency and sustainability within the industry. Join our co-creation workshops and advocacy campaigns to influence policy and raise public awareness. Together, we can ensure the long-term health of our fisheries."	LinkedIn
Aquaculture Associations and Producer Organizations	Sustainable practices, economic benefits, regulatory compliance, industry collaboration, research participation, policy advocacy, staff training	"Aquaculture is a vital part of the seafood industry. By adopting VeriFish indicators, you can demonstrate the sustainability of your operations and enhance market positioning. Participate in our workshops and educational campaigns to lead the way in sustainable aquaculture. Let's work together for a more sustainable industry."	LinkedIn
Policy Stakeholders and Funding Agencies	Policy development, funding opportunities, policy advocacy, impact assessment, stakeholder engagement, sustainability of seafood industries	"Effective policy and funding are crucial for advancing sustainable seafood practices. VeriFish indicators provide a transparent framework to support sustainable seafood policies. Collaborate with us to integrate these indicators into regulations and standards. Join our advocacy efforts to promote responsible sourcing and long-term sustainability."	LinkedIn
Standard Good Practice Organizations	Development and promotion of standards, best practices, support for certification programs, industry collaboration, research contribution	"Standardisation is essential for ensuring the widespread adoption of sustainable practices. VeriFish indicators can be integrated into industry standards to promote sustainability. Join our workshops and advocacy campaigns to develop and promote standardised sustainability indicators. Together, we can drive positive change."	LinkedIn

6. Editorial Plan for VeriFish Project

6.1. Overview

The editorial plan for the VeriFish project serves as a dynamic guide for creating, disseminating, and monitoring content across various platforms to effectively communicate project results and engage stakeholders. It includes diverse content types like news articles, interviews, newsletters, social media activities, and scientific papers, targeting a broad audience. The plan emphasizes open access to all content through repositories like Zenodo and uses regular monitoring via Google Analytics to evaluate impact and refine communication strategies based on feedback and analytics.

Objectives:

- **Disseminate Results:** Ensure widespread dissemination of project outcomes
- **Knowledge Sharing:** Share scientific and technical innovations with stakeholders
- **Stakeholder Engagement:** Targeted communication strategies to support participation
- **Open Access Publication:** FAIR-ification of data as well as promoting transparency
- **Continuous Monitoring and Adjustment:** Targeted adjustment of communication strategies

Monitoring and Adjustment:

- Google Analytics: Regularly monitor digital platform performance and audience engagement.
- Feedback Loop: Analytics to adjust and optimise communication strategies for improvement.
- Stakeholder Feedback: Refining messaging and tactics based on needs and awareness.

6.2. 6 months Editorial plan schedule (August 2024-January 2025)

The six-month editorial plan for VeriFish (Table 4), covering the period from August 2024 to January 2025, is designed to communicate the project's progress, key developments, and stakeholder engagement activities. This plan ensures a consistent flow of information across multiple platforms, keeping stakeholders including citizens and partners well-informed. Each month focuses on specific themes, such as partner spotlights, event coverage, and detailed insights into the VeriFish indicator framework. LinkedIn and X will be utilised as the main channels to amplify reach, while Instagram and Facebook will be used to highlight special events and milestones. Regular content updates, one major post per-week, and interactions will ensure that the project remains visible, relevant, and impactful, driving forward its mission of promoting sustainable fisheries and aquaculture practices.

6.3. Amplifiers and Interactions of VeriFish

The VeriFish editorial plan integrates interactions with stakeholder groups, multipliers, and related research and outreach initiatives to maximise impact. By leveraging a wide range of communication channels and collaborating closely with partner networks, VeriFish ensures that major announcements

and campaigns reach a broad and relevant audience. Targeted stakeholders, including industry professionals, policymakers, and consumer groups, will be engaged through tailored content and outreach activities (Table 5). Additionally, the project will align its efforts with existing research and outreach initiatives to optimise resource use and enhance the dissemination of project results (Table 6). This approach not only broadens the reach of VeriFish’s messages but also fosters collaboration and knowledge-sharing across sectors, avoiding duplication of efforts and ensuring the project’s sustainability and relevance.

Table 4. VeriFish 6-month Editorial Plan (August 2024-January 2025)

Month	Week	Planned Date of Publication	Topic	Responsible	Topic of the Publication
Aug/24	1	01/08/2024	Introduction to the VeriFish Project	Eurofish	Mission and Goals
Aug/24	2	06/08/2024	Partner Spotlight	Trust-It	Introduction of Trust-It
Aug/24	3	13/08/2024	Indicator Framework Overview	EUROFIR	Start Introducing the Indicator Framework
Aug/24	4	20/08/2024	Event Preview: AQUA24	Eurofish	Event Details, Importance for VeriFish
Aug/24	5	27/08/2024	AQUA24 Event Coverage	Eurofish	Highlights, Key Takeaways
Sep/24	1	03/09/2024	Partner Spotlight	COMMpla	Introduction of COMMpla
Sep/24	2	10/09/2024	Indicator Framework: Environmental	Clupea	Detailed Look at the Indicator Framework: Environmental Indicators
Sep/24	3	17/09/2024	Event Preview: Meeting in Tromsø	Eurofish	Event Details, Importance for VeriFish
Sep/24	4	24/09/2024	Meeting in Tromsø Coverage	Eurofish	Highlights, Key Takeaways
Oct/24	1	01/10/2024	Partner Spotlight	FORTH	Introduction of FORTH
Oct/24	2	08/10/2024	Indicator Framework: Social	EUROFIR	Detailed Look at the Indicator Framework: Social Indicators
Oct/24	3	15/10/2024	Event Preview: Conxemar	Eurofish	Event Details, Importance for VeriFish
Oct/24	4	22/10/2024	Conxemar Event Coverage	Eurofish	Highlights, Key Takeaways
Oct/24	5	29/10/2024	Partner Spotlight	NOFIMA	Introduction of NOFIMA

Nov/24	1	05/11/2024	Indicator Framework: Economic	NOFIMA	Detailed Look at the Indicator Framework: Economic Indicators
Nov/24	2	12/11/2024	Future Event Preview	Eurofish	Upcoming Events and Conferences (November and December)
Nov/24	3	19/11/2024	Partner Spotlight	Eurofish	Introduction of Eurofish
Nov/24	4	26/11/2024	Indicator Framework: Consumer Benefits	EUROFIR	How It Helps Consumers Make Informed Choices
Dec/24	1	03/12/2024	Future Plans for VeriFish	Trust-IT	Looking Ahead to 2025
Dec/24	2	10/12/2024	Holiday Message	Eurofish	Thanks to All Partners and Stakeholders
Jan/25	1	03/01/2024	Year-End Review	Eurofish	Key Achievements of the VeriFish Project in 2024
Jan/25	2	08/01/2024	Partner Spotlight	EUROFIR	Introduction of EUROFIR
Jan/25	3	15/01/2024	Indicator Framework Summary	FORTH	Detailed Look at the Indicator Framework: Final Summary and Impact
Jan/25	4	22/01/2024	Partner Spotlight	PMT PI	Introduction of PMT PL

Table 5. Stakeholder groups targeted for Outreach and Dissemination activities

SG#1 Seafood processors and retailers

Direct Seafoods, M&J Seafood, AIPCE.CEP, European Supermarket Magazine, EuroCommerce, Kagerer & Co. GmbH, Delpierre, Antonio Verrini SRL, Blupesca S.R.L, Food Trade International Ltd, FRINSA, FRoSTA, Froxa, Seafoodia, GEREMAR SL, Marked Advisory Council, ANFACO, CONXEMAR, ANICP, Visfederatie, Danish Seafood Association, Central Markets & Fishery Organisation S.A., Seafood Importers & Processors Alliance (SIPA) Belgium, Assoitica Italia, CITPPM France, Alemar SRL.

SG#2 Consumers and consumer associations

EuroCoop, European Consumers Union, Food Watch, The European Consumer Organisation (BEUC), CRIOC, ECU (European Consumers Union), Federconsumatori

SG#3 Children

Copernicus Children for the Oceans, Kids Food Atlas, The Mediterranean Culinary Academy, Global Food Traceability Center, The Oceans and Seafood Markets Initiative (OSMI), Blue Schools project

SG#4 European citizens networks, incl. education and nutrition stakeholders

European Citizens Associations, Fish for tomorrow, ELOR DSC - ConsuMare Giusto, NSAC (North Sea Regional Advisory Council), SEAFOODTOMORROW and their network organisations, public aquariums through UCA Groupement d’Aquariums de France and EAZA (European Association of Zoos and Aquaria)

SG#5 Fisheries / Producer Organisations

EuroPeche, EAPO, Belgian Fish Industry Federation, Vissersbond, Danish Fisherman P.O. Swedish Pelagic Federation, Pelagic Freezer Association, International Seafood Sustainability Association (ISSA), SeaFoodSource, UnderCurrent News, Seafish UK, , Confederação das Organizações Representativas da Pesca Artesanal, FEDERPESCA Italia, LegaPesca, ICHTHYOTROFEIA KEFALONIAS A.E, SetubalPesca, EFFELLE PESCA S.R.L., Azzopardi Fisheries, Micallef Fisheries

SG#6 Aquaculture producers /Producer organisations

Federation of European Aquaculture Producers (FEAP), PO Mosselcultuur, EATiP, APROMAR Espana, Groupement des Mytiliculteurs sur Bouchot, EMPA European Molluscs' Producers Association, Kimagro Fish Farming, Avramar Aquaculture SA, SPAROS, API

SG#7 Policy stakeholders & funding agencies

EUMOFA, European Public Health Alliance, World Wildlife Fund (WWF), Client Earth, PEW Trusts, Oceana, EU Food Policy Coalition, Seas at Risk, IFFO, Fisheries Secretariat, Friends of Ocean Action (WEF), Tuna 2020 Traceability Declaration (WEF), DGPM (Direção-Geral de Política do Mar do Ministério da Economia e Mar, Directorate-General for Maritime Policy), Ministry of Trade, Industry and Fisheries, Norwegian Seafood Council (Norges sjømatråd), DRAPN (Direção Regional de Agricultura e Pescas do Norte), North Atlantic Pelagic Advocacy Group (NAPA).

SG#8 SDOs & standard good practice organisations

Marine Stewardship Council (MSC), Aquaculture Stewardship Council (ASC), GlobalGAP, Friends of the Sea, Ethic Ocean, Good Fish Foundation, Mr Goodfish, Institute for European Environmental Policy, Global Sustainable Seafood Initiative (GSSI), Slow Fish, ACUIPLUS, FASFC (Federal Agency for the Safety of the Food Chain), Global Seafood Alliance, GLOBALG.A.P., Fisheries Transparency Initiative (FITI), FSS (Food Standards Scotland), FSA (Food Standards Agency), The Global Dialogue on Seafood Traceability (GDST), Trade Association for Seafood Traceability Technology (TAST-T), AQUIMER.

Table 6. Research and Outreach initiatives to optimize resource use and enhance the dissemination of project results

Research Projects and initiatives

Performfish www.performfish.eu. Part of the project focuses on designing new ways to address consumer desires and market needs. Their Analysis of consumer perception of seabass and seabream in 4 Mediterranean countries + Germany and UK will be used in the validation phase

FishEUTrust www.fisheustrust.org. Collaboration on consumer engagement to increase trust, safety and traceability and methods for a transparent seafood supply chain

SmartAqua4FuturE. Their analysis of consumer acceptance of freshwater aquaculture production system, benefits of novel feeds on growth and health performances, food safety and robustness metrics to ensure fish welfare, legislative compliance and consumer acceptance will be used building the indicator

EUMOFA - European Market Observatory for Fisheries and Aquaculture Products, Eumofa.eu. Consumption data for seafood products available at national level on a monthly basis

Blue-Cloud2026 www.blue-cloud.org. Collaborative web-based environment providing simplified access to an unprecedented wealth of o multi-disciplinary datasets from observations, analytical services, and computing facilities essential for blue science. One of its V Labs offers the fisheries atlas (with tuna as an example), and the Global Record of Stocks and Fisheries. VeriFish indicator could be offered as a service to the Blue-Cloud2026 hackathon in 2025.

TraceMyFish www.tracemyfish.hi.is research project with the full title of “Traceability and Quality Monitoring throughout the Fish Value Chain” funded by the ERA-NET BlueBio Cofund initiative

Stakeholder networks

The World Benchmarking Alliance (WBA). Its Seafood Stewardship Index (Benchmarking Index Initiative) will be used as a benchmark www.worldbenchmarkingalliance.org/publication/seafood-stewardship-index/

Seafood Task Force www.seafoodtaskforce.global/. Global trade association where the world’s largest retailers, seafood brands and their seafood partners are working together to drive oversight and continuous improvement across the supply chain. To be involved in assessment & outreach

Future of Fish www.futureoffish.org. Nonprofit incubator working with industry players, technologists, and NGOs to create business solutions to ocean challenges. To be involved in outreach campaigns #2 and #3

Provenance www.provenance.org/. Platform that empowers brands to take steps toward greater transparency by tracing the origins and histories of products. To be involved for media product dissemination

International Seafood Sustainability Foundation (ISSF) www.iss-foundation.org. Coalition of acclaimed scientists, seafood industry leaders, and environmental champions launched the International Seafood Sustainability Foundation (ISSF) based on shared concerns about the future of tuna fisheries Will be involved in outreach campaigns.

Global Fishing Watch www.globalfishingwatch.org/ is harnessing innovative technology to turn data into actionable information and drive tangible change in the way that fisheries are governed. To be involved in outreach campaigns

FishWise www.fishwise.org Seafood industry compass, providing innovative market-based tools and expertise in sustainability services, human rights action, traceability best practices. To be involved in media product dissemination

Global Seafood Ratings Alliance www.globalseafoodratings.wordpress.com. The network of seafood sustainability rating initiatives (including Seafood Watch, Mr Goodfish and WWF Germany). To be involved in outreach campaigns

Fish Tales www.fish-tales.com working with fishing communities in developing countries raising consumer awareness on the current state of our oceans and the importance of sustainable fishing. To be involved in storytelling and dissemination activities.

ANNEX 1: Stakeholder Analysis

Table 7. Key topics for each stakeholder groups

Stakeholder Group	Key Topics	Description
Seafood Retailers & HoReCa	Sustainable Fishing Practices	Promoting and sourcing seafood from sustainable fishing practices.
	Economic Benefits	Highlighting the economic advantages of selling sustainably sourced seafood.
	Regulatory Compliance	Ensuring adherence to sustainability standards and regulations.
	Industry Collaboration	Encouraging partnerships with fisheries and aquaculture producers to ensure a steady supply of sustainable seafood.
	Advocacy for Supportive Policies	Working together to advocate for policies that support sustainable fishing and aquaculture practices.
	Training Opportunities	Providing staff with education and training on sustainable seafood practices.
Consumers and Consumer Associations	Sustainable Fishing Practices	Educating consumers on the importance of choosing seafood from sustainable sources.
	Health Benefits	Highlighting the nutritional and health benefits of consuming sustainable seafood.
	Transparency and Trust	Providing clear and verifiable information about the sustainability of seafood products.
	Advocacy for Better Labelling	Promoting better labelling and transparency in seafood sourcing.
	Community Engagement	Encouraging community involvement and participation in sustainable seafood initiatives.
Children (Parents/Educators)	Educational Programs	Developing educational content and programs about sustainable seafood.
	Health and Nutrition	Teaching children about the health benefits of consuming seafood.
	Interactive Learning	Creating interactive and engaging content to make learning about seafood fun and memorable.
	Parental Involvement	Involving parents in educational activities to reinforce learning at home.
	Community and School Events	Organizing events that promote sustainable seafood practices within the community and schools.
European Citizens	Sustainable Seafood Awareness	Raising awareness about the importance of sustainable seafood practices.

	Health Benefits	Highlighting the health benefits of consuming sustainably sourced seafood.
	Environmental Impact	Educating on the environmental benefits of choosing sustainable seafood.
	Advocacy for Policy Changes	Encouraging citizens to support policies that promote sustainable seafood practices.
	Community Engagement	Engaging citizens in community activities that promote sustainable seafood consumption.
Fisheries Associations and Producer Organizations	Sustainable Fishing Practices	Implementing and promoting best practices for sustainable fishing.
	Economic Benefits	Demonstrating the economic advantages of sustainable practices.
	Regulatory Compliance	Ensuring adherence to sustainability standards and regulations.
	Industry Collaboration	Fostering collaboration within the industry to promote sustainability.
	Research Participation	Participating in research initiatives related to sustainable fishing.
	Advocacy for Supportive Policies	Advocating for policies that support sustainable fishing practices.
	Training Opportunities	Providing training and education opportunities for staff on sustainable practices.
Aquaculture Associations and Producer Organizations	Sustainable Aquaculture Practices	Implementing and promoting best practices for sustainable aquaculture.
	Economic Benefits	Demonstrating the economic advantages of sustainable aquaculture practices.
	Regulatory Compliance	Ensuring adherence to sustainability standards and regulations.
	Industry Collaboration	Fostering collaboration within the industry to promote sustainability.
	Research Participation	Participating in research initiatives related to sustainable aquaculture.
	Advocacy for Supportive Policies	Advocating for policies that support sustainable aquaculture practices.
	Training Opportunities	Providing training and education opportunities for staff on sustainable practices.
Policy Stakeholders and Funding Agencies	Policy Development	Developing policies that support sustainable seafood practices.
	Economic Benefits	Highlighting the economic impact of sustainable seafood practices.
	Regulatory Compliance	Ensuring policies support and enforce sustainability standards.
	Industry Collaboration	Encouraging collaboration between policymakers and industry stakeholders.
	Research Funding	Providing funding for research initiatives related to sustainable seafood.
	Advocacy for Sustainability	Promoting advocacy for sustainability within the seafood industry.

Standard Good Practice Organizations	Developing Standards	Creating and promoting standards for sustainable seafood practices.
	Regulatory Compliance	Ensuring standards align with regulatory requirements.
	Industry Collaboration	Working with industry stakeholders to implement and adhere to standards.
	Advocacy for Standards	Promoting the adoption of sustainability standards within the industry.
	Research Participation	Supporting and participating in research to improve and develop standards.

ANNEX 2: VeriFish Website sitemap

VeriFish homepage

- Short project description / teaser
- Latest news
- What we do (Resume)
- Funded by the EU
- Contact details and SoMe links

About VeriFish

- Project summary
- Objectives / Goals
- Specific Objectives
- Work Packages
- Partners

Why Sustainable Seafood Matters

VeriFish web app

- Description of the App

News & Events

- News / Press releases
- Link to EU Magazine

Contact us

The website sitemap will be updated as the webpage will be changed during the project as materials are produced, and the indicator framework and the App develop.

Link: verifish.info

ANNEX 3: Social Media Links

Table 8. VeriFish SoMe channel links

Social media	Link
LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/company/verifishproject/
X	https://x.com/Verfish_project
Instagram	https://www.instagram.com/verifish_project/
Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/profile.php?id=61558684007435
YouTube	https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCdfum4ZZuTvPdj65e7VVZNw
Threads	https://www.threads.net/@verifish_project

